

Scurvy during John Davis' voyage (1591-1593)

by Harri Hemilä

John Davis was one of Queen Elizabeth I's chief navigators. During one of his sea voyages, many crew members developed symptoms consistent with scurvy. This document extracts the relevant textual sections and discusses their interpretation. In his authoritative book, "*The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C*", Kenneth Carpenter claimed about the symptoms described on Davis' voyage that "Obviously this disease was not scurvy". Carpenter's claim is refuted.

Biographies:

"John Davis was one of the chief navigators of Queen Elizabeth I of England. He led several voyages to discover the Northwest Passage and served as pilot and captain on both Dutch and English voyages to the East Indies. He discovered the Falkland Islands in August 1592."

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/John_Davis_\(explorer\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/John_Davis_(explorer))

<https://www.britannica.com/biography/John-Davis>

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

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The earliest recorded outbreak of scurvy on a long sea voyage seems to have occurred during Vasco da Gama's first voyage to India (1497-1499).¹ Thereafter, the disease afflicted vast numbers of sailors throughout the Age of Sail.^{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12} In the English Navy, the incidence of scurvy declined dramatically at the end of the eighteenth century, when lemon juice was made obligatory for seamen.^{4, 13, 14}

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- 1 Scurvy during *Vasco da Gama's* first voyage (1497-1499).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781205>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/46440>
 - 2 Lind J (1772) *A Treatise on the Scurvy*.
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/n5/mode/2up>
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt>
 - 3 Rouppe L (1772) *On the Scurvy*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17227637> Rouppe
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18302180> Lind's summary
 - 4 Carpenter KJ (1986) *The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C: The explorers' sickness*; p.1-28,95-97.
<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>
 - 5 Scurvy during *Magellan's* voyage around the world (1519-1522).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001193>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/42884> Translation by Robertson
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/74723> Translation by Stanley
 - 6 Scurvy during *Thomas Stevens' voyage to India* (1579).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174375>
 - 7 Scurvy during *Richard Hawkins' voyage* (1593).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001137>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/57502>
 - 8 Scurvy during *Sebastián Vizcaíno's* exploration (1602-1603).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18300855> Ascensión
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18301146> Lind's summary
 - 9 *François Pyrard's Description of Scurvy During a Sea Voyage* (1602-1603).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18415628>
 - 10 Scurvy during *Henry Middleton's Voyage* (1604).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18418006>
 - 11 Scurvy on *Anson's* voyage round the world (1740-1744).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17397300>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/16611>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/47130>
 - 12 A fatal scurvy in the East Indies (1762).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299146>
 - 13 Budd G (1840) *Scurvy*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962>
 - 14 Between the years 1779 and 1813, the diminution of sick and of deaths in the British navy was in the proportion of four to one. In 1779, 1:2.45 were sick, and in 1813, 1:10.75 were sick, corresponding to decline by ratio 4.4. Table 1, p.539-540 in:
Blane G (1815) *Statements of the comparative Health of the British Navy, from the year 1779 to the year 1814*.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2129027>

In his authoritative book “*The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C*”, **Kenneth Carpenter** (1986, p.14-15)⁴ summarizes the symptoms reported on the voyage by John Davies as follows:

With the defeat of Spain, British sailors started on new adventures. The first, led again by Thomas Candish, was disastrous. They missed the best season for passing through the Straits [of Magellan], the ships were separated, and Candish died on the way back across the Atlantic. John Davis’s ship, the *Dainty*, got through the Straits only to be driven back, and the crew rested on the Argentine coast; the narrator went on: “In this place we found a herbe called **scurvygrass**, which we fried with eggs, using train oil instead of butter. This herbe did so purge the blood, that **it took away all kinds of swellings, of which many died, and restored us all to perfect health of body, so that we were in as good a case as when we came first out of England.**”¹⁵ “Scurvy grass” can mean the spoonwort *Cochlearia curiosa*, or *officinalis*, or cresses such as *Cardamine glacialis* and *hirsuta*. Train oil was obtained by boiling the carcasses of seals and skimming it off.

While in the same harbor, they killed and dried 20,000 penguins. A storm blew up, and they finally embarked only (!) 14,000. **They planned to make their stock of food last them for a six-month voyage home;** it worked out to include a ration of 1¼ penguins per head per day. Unfortunately, as the sailors went through the Tropics, the inadequately dried and salted birds began to corrupt and harbor loathsome-looking worms. After crossing the Equator,

the men began to fall sick of a monstrous disease: for in their ankles it began to swell, from thence in two days it would be in their breasts, so that they could not draw their breath, and then fell into their cods, and their cods and yarges did swell most grievously and most dreadfully to behold, so that they could neither stand, lie, nor go. Whereupon ... divers grew raging mad, and some died in most loathsome and furious pain... To be short, all our men died except sixteen of which there were but five able to move.¹⁶

Davis and the survivors just managed to bring the ship to the Irish coast and run her ashore. **Obviously this disease was not scurvy.** It has been suggested that it was caused by a parasitic infestation or, more probably, that it was a form of beriberi.¹⁷

Carpenter offers no independent arguments as to why the described symptoms could not represent scurvy; instead, he simply refers to Creighton’s earlier (1891) account,^{17, 18} see the next page.

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- 15 Carpenter ref. 48: A. H. Markham (1980b), 122.
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.181682/page/n235/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.46971/page/n235/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagesandworks00wriggoog/page/122/mode/2up>
- 16 Carpenter ref. 50: A. H. Markham (1980b), 126-7.
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.181682/page/n239/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.46971/page/n239/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagesandworks00wriggoog/page/126/mode/2up>
- 17 Carpenter ref. 51: Creighton (1891), 593.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17882745>
<https://archive.org/details/historyofepidemi01unse/page/592/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/historyofepidemi01crei/page/592/mode/2up>

Charles Creighton's (1891) description and discussion of symptoms on John Davies' voyage:¹⁸

... The narrative (by John Lane), then follows the fortunes of one of the ships, the 'Desire.' Landing at Port Desire, in Patagonia, they found scurvy-grass growing, which they ate with oil: "This herb did so purge the blood that it took away all kind of swellings, of which many [had] died, and restored us to perfect health of body, so that we were in as good case as when we came first out of England." There also they took on board 14,000 penguins, which they had dried on the rocks, mostly without salt; and sailed northwards on December 22. With only 27 men surviving out of 76, they left the coast of Brazil at Cape Frio (near Rio de Janeiro), and then began their more singular experience of disease.

"After we came near unto the sun, our dried penguins began to corrupt, and there bred in them a most loathsome and ugly worm of an inch long. This worm did mightily increase, and devour our victuals;" it devoured everything except iron,—clothes, boots, shirts, even the ship's timbers! "In this woeful case, after we had passed the equinoctial toward the North, our men began to fall sick of such a monstrous disease as I think the like was never heard of: for in their ankles it began to swell, from thence in two days it would be in their breasts, so that they could not draw their breath, and then fell into their cods, and their cods¹⁹ and yarges²⁰ did swell most grievously and most dreadfully to behold, so that they could neither stand, lie, nor goe. Whereupon our men grew mad with grief. Our captain [John Davis] with extreme anguish of his soul was in such woeful case that he desired only a speedy end, and though he were scarce able to speak for sorrow, yet he persuaded them to patience... For all this, divers grew raging mad, and some died in most loathsome and furious pain. It were incredible to write our misery as it was; there was no man in perfect health but the captain, and one boy... To be short, all our men died except sixteen [i.e., eleven died of the survivors after Cape Frio] of which there were but five able to move."

Those five worked the ship into Berehaven (Bantry Bay) on June 11, 1593, and there ran her ashore.

The remarkable epidemic on board the 'Desire,' among men living upon dried penguin infested with worms, was probably not scurvy, or at least not all scurvy: the dropsy and dyspnoea suggest one of the two forms of beri-beri, of a peculiarly severe type. The co-existence of worms in the dried food may lead one to think of a parasitic malady such as that caused by *Anchylostoma duodenale*, which has also an anasaruous or œdematous character. But the diagnosis of beri-beri appears to be far more likely.

18 A history of epidemics in Britain by Creighton, Charles (1891), p.592-593.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17882745>
<https://archive.org/details/historyofepidemi01unse/page/592/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/historyofepidemi01crei/page/592/mode/2up>
<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/001559476>

19 Cods. Testicles.
<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/cod>

20 Yarges. Penis.
https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/%C8%9Derde#Middle_English

Creighton's suggestion that the described symptoms were "probably not scurvy" is unconvincing. The presence of "dropsy and dyspnœa" does not specifically indicate beriberi. Scurvy, too, can produce both edema and dyspnea.

First, on p.593-594, Creighton writes:

in the next that we come to, the sickness on board the 'Daintie,' Richard Hawkins master, on a voyage in 1593 through the Straits of Magellan, the disease is typical scurvy; and the observations on sea-scurvy by Hawkins himself are among the best that we have for the period, and, indeed, until long after the Elizabethan period.

Thereafter follows Creighton's extract from Hawking's journey:

My company within a few days began to fall sick of a disease which seamen are wont to call the scurvie; and seemeth to be a kind of dropsie, ... causeth a general swelling of all parts of the body, especially of the legs, and gums...

Creighton's argument that the symptoms observed on Davis's voyage were not scurvy because they included dropsy²¹ is illogical. At the same time, he maintains that Hawkins's account contains one of the best descriptions of scurvy, even though Hawkins identified "dropsie" as a prominent symptom.

Second, scurvy can lead to heart failure,²² which may account for symptoms such as swelling and dyspnea. In addition, vitamin C administration has been shown in some contexts to reduce bronchoconstriction.²³ Therefore, vitamin C deficiency may contribute to dyspnea not only through cardiac complications but also via non-cardiac mechanisms.

Third, pain is a very typical symptom of scurvy.²⁴

21 Dropsy.

The historical diagnosis of dropsy – which is now obsolete – indicated simply an abnormal accumulation of fluid. The word derives from the Greek hydro (water). Alternative or supplementary terms included hydrothorax (fluid in the chest cavity), ascites (which still indicates excess free fluid in the abdominal cavity), anasarca (still used to describe generalized edema throughout the body).

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CHOL9780521332866.101>

An ancient medical term used to indicate different conditions including chronic heart failure.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2017.07.104>

22 Scurvy can cause heart failure, which can cause swellings and dyspnea, e.g.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38504249>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35282368>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38464798>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27682441>

23 Vitamin C can reduce bronchoconstriction in some contexts, e.g.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24279478>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25788952>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23794586>

24 Pain in the legs is a very common symptom of scurvy, e.g.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15797491>

Fourth, swelling of testicles [cods] was described by Van der Mye in the siege of Breda (1624) (James Lind's summary): "Watery swellings of the testicles were frequent"²⁵, by Nitzsch about scurvy in Vyborg (1732, 1734) (Lind's summary): "The feet, scrotum and belly were sometimes greatly distended with a transparent watery swelling"²⁶, in an outbreak of scurvy in a US squadron in the East Indies (Lind's summary): "This swelling afterwards extending itself to the belly and scrotum,"²⁷ and in another outbreak described by Lind (1772, p.542): "after a passage of three months, many of our men were afflicted with dropsical swellings of the legs; the scrotum in some contained a gallon of water."²⁸ Lind also wrote (1772, p.125-126): "... two patients fell under my cure... The disease still gained ground, he was suddenly seized with a large watery swelling of scrotum."²⁹

Thus, "their cods ... did swell" report on Davis' voyage is also consistent with several other scurvy reports.

Fifth, Carpenter noted that "They planned to make their stock of food last them for a six-month voyage home." In the absence of proper storage methods to preserve lemons or other fruit for a six-month voyage in that time, it is evident that the crew would have begun to suffer from vitamin C deficiency as the journey progressed.

Sixth, Beriberi is caused by a deficiency of thiamine. Meat is a good source of thiamine, and although the penguin meat consumed during the voyage had spoiled, it is unlikely that the crew's thiamine intake was entirely absent. In contrast, during prolonged sea voyages without access to fresh plant foods, vitamin C intake would have been nonexistent.

Seventh, Beriberi emerged as a significant public health problem only in the late nineteenth century, when polished white rice became widely available. The technology required to produce white rice was developed in the nineteenth century, and such rice was not commonly available at the end of the sixteenth century. As David Arnold summarizes:³⁰

Medical historians have recounted the pioneering identification of the disease in maritime Asia, the growing incidence observed during the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries... the general recognition by about 1910 of the connection between beriberi and diets of milled "white" rice. p.296

... Across much of monsoon Asia beriberi appeared to be a very modern disease. For this there were several explanations. Since the 1870s there had been the rapid growth of mechanized rice-milling. Instead of de-husking by hand, rice was now processed in power-driven mills, which, along with the husk, removed the inner skin or pericarp, the grain then being further buffeted to produce a polished, white appearance. In removing the thiamine contained in the pericarp, milling exposed consumers whose diet consisted almost entirely of white rice to the risk of beriberi. Rice polishings containing the vital nutrients removed by milling were thrown away or fed to animals. Milling fuelled a revolution in taste. The demand for hand-pounded rice fell: white rice was sought after as more palatable, more prestigious and might even be cheaper. Milling also reduced the bulk of rawpaddy by a third, making rice more economical to transport and less prone to deterioration when stored and shipped. With the growth of massive exports from Burma, Thailand and Vietnam into the p.303

25 Description of scurvy by Vander Mye (1624).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17225428>

26 Description of scurvy in Vyborg by Nitzsch (1732, 1734).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17295494>

27 A fatal scurvy in the East Indies (1762).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299146>

28 <https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/542/mode/2up>

29 <https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/124/mode/2up>

30 Arnold D. British India and the "beriberi problem", 1798-1942. Med Hist. 2010;54(3):295-314.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20592882>

Philippines, Indonesia, and increasingly by the 1920s into India, the regional trade in milled rice expanded enormously—and with it beriberi.

K Codell Carter described the history of beri-beri as follows:³¹

Beriberi ... Prior to the nineteenth century, the disease was relatively unimportant even in the orient... modern steammilling procedures, which we now recognize to have been substantially responsible for the rise of beriberi, did not become common in Asia until then. By the last quarter of the nineteenth century the disease was widespread and growing at an extraordinary rate... p.124

We can, somewhat arbitrarily, take 1880 as the beginning of serious occidental interest in beriberi... It was obvious to everyone that the disease was predominant only in areas where rice was the staple diet... p.125

Thus, beriberi as a public health problem was explained by the use of white rice, but white rice became cheaper and popular only in the late 1800s. Beriberi was a substantial problem in the Japanese Navy in the late 1800s, and Takaki found that increasing the intake of protein eliminated the disease.³² Beriberi was still a relatively new disease when Creighton published his book in 1891. Contemporary discussions may have influenced him to speculate that beriberi might account for some earlier reports of sailors' illnesses. However, a proposal that thiamine-deficient white rice—consumed as the sole food source—explains the symptoms described at the end of the 1500s during Davis's voyage is not reasonable.

Eight, Axel Holst (1907) concluded that the so-called “ship-beri-beri” was scurvy:³³

AMONG the diseases which have of late attracted the attention of the official medical authorities of Norway, so-called *ship-beri-beri* takes a prominent place. The symptoms of this disease consist, in the great majority of cases, in weakness and a prominent dropsy of the lower limbs, extending often to other parts of the body. There also exists shortness of breath and other symptoms of a weak heart, causing often sudden deaths from acute paralysis of the heart. But as Nocht in Hamburg and the *Norwegian Ship-beri-beri Committee* have shown, symptoms of neuritis of the limbs are comparatively rare. For instance, Nocht was only able to ascertain neuritis in cases from four of his thirty-four beri-beri-ships; and though the investigations of the Committee extended to fifty-seven affected ships, the neuritis was only found in men from four of them. Considering that neuritis is the essential symptom of the beri-beri of tropical countries and Japan, and that dropsy, though present, as a rule is not prominent in cases of this disease, it seems, therefore, rather doubtful whether ship-beri-beri is identical with tropical beri-beri. This doubt, first emphasized by Bullmore³⁴ and Nocht, is strengthened by the fact that the great majority of patients suffering from the ordinary, i.e. dropsical ship- p.619

31 Carter KC. The germ theory, beriberi, and the deficiency theory of disease. *Med Hist.* 1977;21(2):119-36. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/325303>

32 Sugiyama Y, Seita A. Kanehiro Takaki and the control of beriberi in the Japanese Navy. *J R Soc Med.* 2013 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23897451>

33 Holst A. Experimental studies relating to “Ship-beri-beri” and scurvy. *J Hyg (Lond).* 1907;7(5):619-33. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20474336>

34 Holst's footnote:

Bullmore, C. Beri-beri. *Lancet* 1900;156(Sept 22):873-875.

“... I do not consider that what we in England call beri-beri is beri-beri – at least, not such as is met with in foreign countries.”

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(01\)97883-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(01)97883-3)

disease, recover as soon as they are able to change their food, which is not the case with the disease of the tropics and Japan.

p.620

The subject of this and the following articles will be limited to experiments relating to the dependence of the ship-disease on food, the etiology of tropical beri-beri being outside the field of these investigations.

The recovery of patients suffering from ship-beri-beri is due to *fresh food*. This fact has chiefly been emphasized by Nocht, while the report of the Norwegian Committee contains many corresponding observations. No doubt, some cases do not appear to agree with this observation, which fact, perhaps, favours the idea that "ship-beri-beri" occasionally comprehends more than one disease. This idea may possibly also be supported by the occurrence of cases of neuritis. But *in the great majority of cases the effect of fresh animal food, such as eggs or meat, but above all of fresh green vegetables or potatoes, is very marked.* For instance, Nocht has pointed out that the symptoms regularly disappear within 8-14 days after the patients get fresh food: even after 4-5 days many patients feel able to resume their work.

...

Apart from the sore gums and haemorrhages in the skin and muscles, which Nocht observed in cases from twelve of his thirty-four ships, but which the Norwegian Committee could not find, it therefore seems probable, that ship-beri-beri is, in accordance with the opinion of Nocht, a food disease, showing a marked congruence with scurvy.

That the malady is a form of scurvy (Nocht) or related to it (Nocht and the Norwegian Committee), is also supported by the fact, quoted by Nocht, that cases of dropsy without haemorrhages or sore gums often occur during epidemics of manifest scurvy. For instance, Nocht quotes authors relating a considerable number of cases of this kind in the epidemic of scurvy, during the siege of Paris in 1870-71. He has further stated, that such cases often occur during epidemics of scurvy in Russia. I may add that many dropsical cases without sore gums and hemorrhages were also observed during the Crimean war where scurvy was very prevalent. (Some of these Crimean cases were connected with anaesthesia of the feet and looked like "acrodynie" or beri-beri; but as they were sometimes associated with a local gangrene of the feet or with distinct symptoms of scurvy, the opinion prevailed that they were due to the cold of the winter in addition to latent or manifest scurvy.) It may further be mentioned, that many cases of dropsy without sore gums, &c. occur every year besides manifest scurvy on board the French vessels fishing for 5-6 months on the banks of Newfoundland. Finally I may add, that during the first part of the 19th century not only scurvy, but also dropsy without sore gums and haemorrhages was very common in European and American prisons. For instance, besides typhoid fever and consumption, this "prison-dropsy" (*Wassersucht der Gefangnisse*) is stated, in 1847, to have been the most prevalent cause of death in 41 prisons in England, France and North America. In 1857 it caused one half of the deaths in a prison in Breslau; and if it were not that nothing is said about the occurrence of neuritis, some reports from those days recall the descriptions of the Asiatic beri-beri-prisons of our own time...

p.621

Axel Holst³⁵ was not a peripheral researcher in nutrition.
For example, Kenneth Carpenter wrote about him as follows:⁴

The year 1907 saw the publication of what I judge to have been the most important single paper in the whole history of this subject [scurvy]. Its importance came not from its having any immediate practical result, but because it provided an animal model for systematic study of the preventive value of different substances, so that the identification of the antiscorbutic factor would now become almost inevitable. The authors were two Norwegians working at the University of Christiania (Oslo). The first author, *Axel Holst*, was forty-seven years old and Professor of Hygiene and Bacteriology; he had studied in various European laboratories... p.173

McCullum... said that "*Holst* and Frölich's description in 1907 of the experimental production of scurvy in guinea pigs fed dry or cooked diets, and its cure by feeding fresh vegetables or fruits, was a highly important contribution. It not only confirmed the vitamin hypothesis, but made available experimentally-induced scurvy in animals for study of the nature of the anti-scorbutic vitamin." p.183

... it was only in this century, through the chance use by *Holst* and Frölich of guinea pigs, one of the few animal species that do require the antiscorbutic factor, that real progress began to be made [in understanding scurvy]. p.250

... the people such as Bachstrom, Lind, Elliotson, Budd, and *Holst*, who made contributions and drew conclusions that we now consider well founded, seem equally consistently to have escaped the usual marks of general recognition and appreciation. p.251

Therefore, great weight should to be put on Holst's opinion on the nature of "ship beri-beri".

Ninth, the lack of benefit from "lime-juice" does not indicate that the disease was not scurvy.

It is not clear how much beriberi became a potential explanation because lime-juice did not benefit the sick sailors.

Axel Holst (1907) commented (after the text extracted above):³⁶

Finally, it may be mentioned that beri-beri has often appeared on Norwegian ships in spite of a daily use of lime-juice. But, it is true, this point has not been quite cleared up; the juice may, for instance, have been adulterated. p.623

This is not speculation. The problem of adulteration was known already a century before Holst's comments. For example, Thomas Trotter (1804) *Medicina Nautica*, vol. III, wrote:

"Indeed it is pretty certain that what was called lemon-juice in the victualling-office, was only acetous acid and lemon-juice mixed. The importation of lemons to this country must have been unequal to the expenditure in the navy only. But it is also probable that if the juice was unadulterated, it had been weakened and diluted by other means." p.389.³⁷

35 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Axel_Holst
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/13163751>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(00\)90725-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(00)90725-6)

36 Holst A. Experimental studies relating to "Ship-beri-beri" and scurvy. *J Hyg (Lond)*. 1907;7(5):619-33.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20474336>

37 https://archive.org/details/b33088810_0003/page/388/mode/2up

“Besides, the acid may be so diluted and weakened by the addition of pure water, so as very much to disappoint us in the cure, unless exhibited in very large quantity. When mixed with acetous acid, I believe no chemical test can decide the sophistication” p.391.³⁸

In 1854, William Burnett wrote:

It is notorious, however, that the lemon-juice supplied has for many years been very inferior in quality ...³⁹

In 1919, Alice Smith wrote:

The purity of the supply for the Navy was always a matter of much care and concern, and there was difficulty, and sometimes failure, in securing it from adulteration. As was natural, injured or decayed fruit that was not fit to be shipped was made into “lime juice,” and in 1853 we find the statement without comment in a medical work, “Lemon juice has long been regarded as an invaluable antiscorbutic; but, on account of the difficulty of preserving it, crystallized citric acid is usually substituted.” ... Sir James Ross’s expedition of 1848 returned in 1849 with a report of a serious outbreak. The lemon juice supplied to his ships was examined and was found to lack nine parts in ten of the proper acid content. p.8-9.⁴⁰

Furthermore, in the guinea pig-model, lime-juice – mentioned by Holst – was shown to contain only one fourth of the antiscorbutic activity than lemon juice in the early 1900s:

The antiscorbutic value of the juice of fresh limes (*Citrus medica*, var. *acida*) has been compared experimentally with that of fresh lemons (*Citrus medica*, var. *limonum*) and has been found to be distinctly inferior. Volume for volume fresh lime juice possesses a potency of about one-fourth that of lemon juice. ... Preserved lime juice was found useless for the prevention of scurvy by the method employed.

The experimental results are fully confirmed by a historical study of “lime juice” in connexion with human scurvy. At the period when scurvy was eliminated from the British Navy by its agency the term was used to express the juice of lemons, and it was not until the second half of the nineteenth century that the juice of West Indian limes was adopted in the Navy and Mercantile Marine... p.738.⁴¹

Finally, vitamin C is easily destroyed by heat and contact with oxygen. For example, Chick et al. found that preserved lime juice had no antiscorbutic activity, although fresh did have.³⁶

Thus, the absence of benefit from lime juice in historical reports does not demonstrate that the disease in question was not scurvy. The lime juice may have been adulterated, improperly stored, or degraded with age; and even when fresh, it contains substantially less vitamin C than an equivalent volume of fresh lemon juice. Greater weight should be given to the converse evidence: when lemon or lime juice clearly cured patients, this strongly supports the conclusion that the illness was scurvy.

38 https://archive.org/details/b33088810_0003/page/390/mode/2up

39 Burnett W. Medical Times and Gazette, 1854
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18483342>

40 Smith AH. A historical inquiry into the efficacy of lime-juice for the prevention and cure of scurvy. J R Army Med Corps, 1919
<https://zenodo.org/records/18484405>

41 Chick H, EM Hume, RF Skelton, Smith AH. The relative content of antiscorbutic principle in limes and lemons. Lancet 1918.
<https://zenodo.org/records/18543473>

These arguments refute Kenneth Carpenter's statement that "Obviously this disease was not scurvy".

Creighton wrote that the disease was "not all scurvy" which is quite different when compared with Carpenter's categorical rejection of scurvy.

When the sailors on John Davis' voyage were eating spoiled penguin meat, they may have suffered from infections. Furthermore, the poor quality and bad taste of foods evidently caused that the sailors were eating much less than their physiological need, and this may have led to some level of general starvation. However, these considerations do not negate the fact that half-a-year voyage without fruit or other plant foods led to scurvy at that period of history, and the reported symptoms are consistent with scurvy, whereas beriberi was a relevant problem only two centuries later.

Swelling of gums is common in scurvy, but that is not mentioned in the journal of Davis' voyage. Many experts on scurvy, who have treated numerous patients, have emphasized that there are substantial variations in the symptoms between patients and thus it is possible that the swelling of gums was not as marked as during some other voyages. See also above Holst's notes on scurvy causing dropsy but not gum diseases.

Furthermore, lack of reporting a particular symptom does not directly indicate that the symptom was missing. James Lind pointed out that none of the early descriptions of scurvy were written by physicians and "it was regretted that those [accounts of voyages] were the productions only of seamen; and that no physician conversant with this disease at sea, had undertaken to throw light upon the subject."⁴² Symptoms missing from the report of a physician may somewhat more confidently indicate that the particular symptom was not observed.

For these reasons, the conclusion in this report is that scurvy is at least one of the explanations for the symptoms described on John Davis' voyage (1591-1593), though it is evident that other diseases may have occurred simultaneously.

The sections below are the of the voyage by John Davis that describe the symptoms.

42 Lind J (1772) Treatise on the Scurvy, p.ix.
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=15>

The voyages and works of John Davis, the navigator, p.121-123,126-128

<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.46971/page/n239/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.181682/page/n239/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/voyagesandworks00wriggoog/page/126/mode/2up>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=aeu.ark:/13960/t0rr29d3h&seq=249>

At their returne they sent the boate to the Isle of Pen- p.121
guins; whereby wee understood that the Penguins dried
to our hearts content, and that the multitude of them was
infinite. This Penguin hath the shape of a bird, but hath
no wings, only two stumps in the place of wings, by which
he swimmeth under water with as great swiftnes as any fish.

They live upon smelts, whereof there is great abundance
upon this coast: in eating they be neither fish nor flesh:
they lay great eggs, and the bird is of a reasonable bignes,
very neere twice so big as a ducke. All the time that wee p.122
were in this place, we fared passing well with eggs, Penguins,
yong Seales, yong Gules, besides other birds, such as I
know not: of all which we had great abundance. In this
place we found an herbe called **Scurvygrasse**,⁴³ which wee
fried with eggs, using traine oyle⁴⁴ in stead of butter.

**This herbe did so purge ye blood, that it tooke away all kind of
swellings, of which many died, and restored us to perfect
health of body**,⁴⁵ so that we were in as good case as when we
came first out of England. We stayed in this harbour until
the 22 of December, in which time we had dried 20,000
Penguins; and the Captaine, the Master, and myselfe, had
made some salt, by laying salt water upon the rocks in
holes, which in 6 daies would be kernered.⁴⁶ Thus God did
feed us even, as it were, with Manna from heaven.

The 22 of December we departed with our ship for the
Isle, where with great difficulty, by the skilful industry of
our Master we got 14,000 of our birds, and had almost lost

43 Note in the text:

Cochlearia Officinalis, a cruciferous plant. It is supposed to be an
excellent antiscorbutic, and is much used in cases of scurvy by the
natives of Greenland and other northern regions. It grows in great
quantities in the Arctic zone, usually about 200 feet above the level of
the sea, flowering from June to August.

44 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Whale_oil

https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/train_oil

45 Note by HH:

Benefit from plants such as scurvy-grass is consistent with the disease being scurvy.
However, the text on the following pages (p.126-127) does not indicate whether
they considered that the symptoms of the second disease were similar to the symptoms experienced here. If
they were, then the benefit from plants in this context would support the conclusion that the second disease
was also scurvy.

46 Kernered. Thickened.

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kerning_\(dairy\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kerning_(dairy))

our captaine in labouring to bring the birds aboard: and had not our Master bene very expert in the set of those wicked tides, which run after many fashions, we had also lost our ship in the same place: but God of his goodnes hath in all our extremities bene our protector. So the 22, at night, we departed with 14,000 dried Penguins, not being able to fetch the rest, and shaped our coarse for Brasil.

Nowe our captaine rated our victuals, and brought us to such allowance, as that **our victuals might last sixe moneths; for our hope was, that within sixe moneths we might recover our country,** though our sailes were very bad. So the allowance was two ounces and a halfe of meale for a man a day, and to have so twice a weeke, so that 5 ounces did serve for a weeke. Three daies a weeke we had oile, three spoonfuls for a man a day; and 2 dayes in a weeke peason, a pint betweene 4 men a day, and every day 5 Penguins for 4 men, and 6 quartes of water for 4 men a day. **This was our allowance; wherewith (we praise God) we lived, though weakly, and very feeble.**

p.123

The 30 of January we arrived at the Ile of Placencia in Brasill ... Then the captaine went to the gardens, and brought from thence fruits and roots for the company, and came aboard the ship, and brought her into a fine creeke which he had found out, where we might more her by the trees, and where there was water, and hoopes to trim our caske. Our case being very desperate, we presently laboured for dispatch away...

The 3 of February, our men, with 23 shot, went againe to the gardens, being 3 miles from us upon the North shore, and fetched Cazavi-roots out of the ground, to relieve our company instead of bread; for we spent not of our mealo while we staid here.

...

In this distresse it pleased Grod to send us raine in such plenty, as that wo wero wel watered and in good comfort to returne.

p.126

But after we came neere unto the sun, our dried Penguins began to corrupt, and there bred in them a most lothsome and ugly worme of an inch long. This worme did so mightily increase and devoure our victuals, that there was in reason no hope how we should avoide famine, but be devoured of these wicked creatures: there was nothing that they did not devoure, only yron excepted: our clothes, boots, shooes, hats, shirts, stockings: and, for the ship,

they did so eat the timbers as that we greatly feared they would undoe us by gnawing through the ships side. Great was the care and diligence of our captaine, master, and company to consume these vermine, but the more we laboured to kill them the more they increased; so that at the last we could not sleepe for them, for they would eate our flesh and bite like Mosquitos. In this wofull case, after we had passed the Equinoctiall toward the North, our men began to fall sick of such a monstrous disease, as I thinke the like was never heard of: for in their ankles it began to swell; from thence in two daies it would be in their breasts, so that they could not draw their breath, and then fell into their cods; and their cods and yarges did swell most grievously and most dreadfully to behold, so that they could neither stand, lie, nor goe. Whereupon our men grew mad with griefe. Our captaine with extreme anguish of his soule was in such wofull case that he desired only a speedie end, and though he were scarce able to speake for sorrow, yet he perswaded them to patience, and to give God thanks, and, like dutifull children, to accept of his chastisement. For all this, divers grew raging mad, and some died in most lothsome and furious paine. It were incredible to write our misery as it was: there was no man in perfect health but the captaine and one boy. The master being a man of good spirit with extreme labour bore out his griefe, so that it grew not upon him. To be short, all our men died except 16, of which there were but 5 able to moove. The captaine was in good health, the master indifferent, captaine Cotton and myselfe swolne and short winded, yet better then the rest that were sicke, and one boy in health: upon us 5 only the labour of the ship did stand.⁴⁷ The captaine and master, as occasion served, would take in and heave out the top sailes, the master onely attended on the sprit-saile, and all of us at the capsten without sheats and tacks.

p.127

In fine, our miserie and weaknesse was so great, that we could not take in nor heave out a saile: so our top-saile and sprit-sailes were torne all in pieces by the weather. The master and captaine taking their turnes at the helme, were

47 Note in the text:

Sixty out of seventy-six men perished during this disastrous voyage. It is a remarkable and noteworthy fact, that the four men who suffered least were officers who lived together in the cabin, and we may safely infer that the boy here alluded to as remaining in good health, was the cabin-boy or attendant of the officers, and therefore lived aft, and presumably on better fare and in a better atmosphere than the seamen.

mightily distressed and monstrously grieved with the most wofull lamentation of our sick men. Thus, as lost wanderers upon the sea, the 11 of June, 1593, it pleased God that we arrived at Bear-haven in Ireland, and there ran the ship on shore: where the Irish men helped us to take in our sailes, and to more our ship for floating; which slender paines of theirs cost the captaine some ten pounds before he could have the ship in safetie. Thus, without victuals, sailes, men, or any furniture, God onely guided us into Ireland, where the captaine left the master and three or four of the company to keepe the ship: and within 5 dayes after he and certaine others had passage in an English fisher-boat to Padstow in Cornewall. In this maner our small remnant by Gods onely mercie were preserved, and restored to our country, to whom be all honour and glory, world without end.

p.128